

What Adults can learn about Young Children's Scribbles

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Abstract

This paper explores the process of scribbling and its product – the scribbles – made by young children aged between 15 months old and 60 months old, and what the process and product of scribbling are all about, starting with the common definitions of scribble and scribbling. The authors went on to differentiate scribbling from doodling and drawing, and also delved into the developmental phases of the scribbling process and its scribbles. More importantly, the paper touches on the why of scribbling, what of the scribbles, i.e., their psycho-symbolic meanings, and the how of adults supporting the development of young children's scribbling through encouragement and dialoguing with these young scribblers. Through the process of scribbling and the interpretation of the varied scribbles produced as well as dialoguing with the scribbler concerned, the authors firmly believe the approach offers an excellent alternative therapy to work with socio-emotionally troubled or disturbed young children who are less verbal or unable to express their feelings and thoughts clearly. They have named it *Dialogic Scribble Therapy*.

Key Words: Color Interpretation, Developmental Phases, Dialoguing, Doodling, Psycho-symbolic Meaning, Scribbles, Scribbling

Introduction

Scribbling is generally defined as a subconscious process involving aimless writing or drawing hurriedly without heed to style or legibility (Liang, 2021; Rabach, 1972; Watts, 2005). It is often taken to be a part of natural instinct of human behavior that involves playing, processing and manipulating, and usually comes naturally as a young child explores, experiences and discovers many new things in his/her immediate environment.

In literature, scribbling and doodling are often used interchangeably. According to Rabach (1972), he described doodles as aimless designs that are absent-mindedly rendered while one's thoughts wander elsewhere. Rostron (2021) also defined scribbles as

being aimless for play or idle improvisation. Watts (2005) defined doodles as self-expressed pictures usually produced in a semi-automatic manner when the mind is in a preoccupied or trance-like state of consciousness. Andrade (2009) described doodling as “just something to relieve the boredom” (p. 4) that those who doodle “do it in a fairly naturalistic, automatic fashion” (p. 4). Qutub (2012) described “doodling as a foolish or wasteful action” (p. 72). Chia and Liu (2020) identified scribbles, doodles and drawings as three different types or forms of printing markings on a given surface regardless of its texture, area and/or size (also see Liang, 2021, for further detail). Table 1 below shows the three different markings (Chia & Liu, 2020).

Table 1. Three Types of Markings

Marking	Type/Form	Intent
Scribble	Graphomotor	No meaningful intent (possibly hidden meanings)
Doodle	Grapho-Psychomotor	Partially indicative of mood (e.g., boredom)
Drawing	Psychomotor	Meaningful intent (pre-writing skill)

Liang (2021) summed up nicely about scribble as follows: “some kind of a marking (i.e., t can be

writing, doodle or drawing) that is carelessly and/or hastily done” (p. 56). She cautioned readers not to

confuse a scribble with a squiggle “which is a short twisting or wiggling line or mark” (Liang, 2021, p. 56).

Four Developmental Stages of Scribbling & Its Scribbles

Children begin to scribble roughly at the age of 15 months old and continue until they are four to five years old. Scribbling has got various phases and each of these phases reflects a child’s developmental milestones. There are generally four stages of drawing and writing from 15 months old to 3 years of age (Sprout Child Development, 2023):

- (1) Random Scribbling between 15 months and 2.5 years old;
- (2) Controlled Scribbling between 2 and 3 years old;
- (3) Lines and Patterns between 2.5 and 3.5 years old; and
- (4) Pictures of Objects or People between 3 and 5 years old.

The authors of this paper have decided to rename the different developmental stages based on the

evolving developmental types of scribbling to emphasize on the main theme of scribbling:

- (1) Random Scribbling (retained);
- (2) Regulated Scribbling (renamed);
- (3) Patterned Scribbling (although the authors used the term *Repeated Scribbling* initially); and
- (4) Imaginal Scribbling (which also involves *imaginativity*¹).

In short, the four developmental stages can be abbreviated to 2R-P-I model. However, it must be emphasized here that the chronological development of scribbling phases listed in Table 2 are approximate. There are no two children develop and/or master these skills at the same pace. Some of them master the skills faster while others, can be slower but still all of them are developing just fine. Parents and teachers should not, therefore, take this growth that must happen at the same speed for every child. What is more important is to offer repeated fun experiences with a wide variety of art activities that allow young children to explore and experiment new things through novel ways of self-expression.

Table 2. 2R-P-I Model: Developmental Phases of Scribbling

Developmental Stage	Developmental Period	Development of Scribbling
Stage #1	15 months-30 months	Random Scribbling
Stage #2	24 months-36 months	Regulated Scribbling
Stage #3	30 months-42 months	Patterned Scribbling
Stage #4	36 months-60 months	Imaginal Scribbling

Stage 1: Random Scribbling (15 months to 2 1/2 years)

According to Sprout Child development (2023), this stage occurs during the period when young children are just beginning to figure out their grapho-movements (with fist grasp; see Figure 1 below) result in the lines (sketchy, wavy, curvy, circular, and zigzag) and scribbles they see on a white sheet of paper or any page. These scribbles made young children are often the result of gross motor movements from the shoulder, with the scribbling implement (e.g., pencil, crayon or marker) held in a fist grasp (Ahmadein & Elharty, 2017). It is during this stage of Random Scribbling that many young children enjoy the scribbling activity and they take pleasure in getting feedback from their senses, e.g., the stickiness and smell of paint, the texture of the surface where scribbling takes place, the squishiness of the clay. For some younger children, they might feel either overwhelmed by too much

sensory information and do not enjoy such sensory art activities (e.g., finger-printing or palm painting). As they grow older, many will learn to tolerate more sensory input, and such sensory art activities (e.g., tactile-based art activities) can be incrementally re-introduced into their routine.

Stage 2: Regulated Scribbling (2 years to 3 years)

As young children grow and mature, they develop a better control over their muscles, especially their hands and fingers. This in turn can be observed in their scribbles, which also begin to change and become more regulated. Toddlers at this age may make repeated markings on surface (e.g., wall and paper) including open-ended circles, diagonal lines, wavy and curvy lines, horizontal and vertical lines. It is also during this phase that transition is observed in young children as they begin to hold the pencil, crayon or marker between their thumb and index finger.

¹ The term *imaginativity* is coined by Chia (2011) to denote “the ability to reproduce mental images as a result of apprehending the textual and/or non-textual experiences by means of the senses or of the mind, or to recombine previous experiences in producing new

images directed at a specific goal or aiding in solving a problem” (p. 26).

It is during this stage that the proper pencil grasp development (see Ahmadein & Elharty, 2017, for more detail) begins to take place in the following sequence (see Figure 1) from 24 months onward with palmar grasp:

(1) Fisted Grasp (12 months-20 months), which coincides with the stage of Random Scribbling.

(2) Palmar Grasp (24 months-36 months), which happens during the stage of Regulated Scribbling.

(3) Static 5-4 Finger Grasp (42 months-48 months), which takes place toward the end of the stage of Patterned Scribbling; and

(4) Dynamic Tripod Grasp (48 months-72 months), which happens the midst of the stage of Imaginal Scribbling.

Figure 1. Stages of Pencil Grasp Development (12 months to 72 months)

Stage 3: Patterned Scribbling (2 1/2 years to 3 1/2 years)

During this stage, young children understand better that handwriting begins with the production of lines, curves, and repeated patterns. These children attempt to copy such graphomotor patterns to create their own handwriting or writing. While they still do not form or produce actual alphabetic letters, adults can observe in their patterned scribbling the apparent components of letters, which might include lines, dots and curves (Sprout Child Development, 2023). This is an exciting moment when the young child recognizes and realizes that his/her scribbling conveys some kind of meaning. For example, a young child may scribble something on a sheet of paper and narrates to the adult what the word-like

scribble says. This is an essential step moving toward literacy (reading and writing) development.

Stage 4: Imaginal Scribbling (3 years to 5 years)

Finally, the last stage concerns Imaginal Scribbling, which refers to a young child's ability to hold an image in the mind and then represent it on a sheet or paper. This process involves a very important thinking skill that young children at this stage of development are attempting to master: what Chia (2011) termed it as *imaginativity*. Adults (i.e., parents and early childhood teachers) can observe their preschool charges scribbling a picture and then labeling their masterpiece with the names of all kinds of objects, animals and people that they are familiar in their daily encounter.

Figure 2. Stages of Scribbling Development in Young Children

Why of Scribbling & Its Scribbles

Scribbling is an essential modality for young children because it allows “them to express their complex thoughts and abstract ideas” (Uddin, 2016, p. 1) that are too difficult for them to express in words, spoken and/or written. Kress (1997) provided an explanation to say that young children could form symbolic thoughts and would use any object/thing available to them or items around them to express their thinking. Torrey (1989) argued that scribbles or doodles can reflect more than one’s emotions and states of mind, but also reflect one’s identity, religion, and values. Malchiodi (1998) strongly believed and argued that children’s scribbles reflect their inner worlds, and the process of scribbling allows them to communicate their feelings within the heart and hidden ideas in the mind that they have yet to be able to express verbally. In other words, scribbles are just like words in a language that embody the thinking of these young children by giving them a channel of expressing their worlds and constructing the meaning of their experiences (Anning, 1999; Bagbhan, 2007).

Young children scribble for various reasons. They scribble to express their emotion or state of mind in order to manage their boredom or frustration (Rostron, 2021). It can also be a reflection of their identity to their peers or significant others (e.g., siblings, parents and teachers). Scribbling, according to Qutub (2012), “help maintain emotional balance when one is bored, frustrated or preoccupied” (p. 73). It also takes place “when open expression is not possible ... in a situation where free verbal self-expression is prohibited” (Qutub, 2012, p. 73) and experienced more by adults than children in this regard in order to “compensate for their inability to speak their mind” (p. 73). Visual symbols are also used to replace speech: an indirect means of conscious expression (Petrovsky, 2009).

According to Anning (1999), scribbling as a process serves as an excellent avenue for developing the fine motor skills of these young children. Scribbling implements (e.g., chalks, color pencils, crayons and markers) are useful tools that allow young children to develop their dexterity and also eye-hand coordination – skills that are essential for gradual development of future writing skills (Uddin, 2016). Moreover, manipulative skills required for letter formation at later developmental stage (e.g., in language arts; see Jalongo, 2007, for detail) can be promoted and enhanced through scribbling activities that involve scrawling lines (e.g., straight line, curves, zigzag lines and wavy lines) and drawing different shapes (e.g., circle, square, triangle and diamond) as shown in Kellogg’s (1969/1970) large collection of scribbles done by preschoolers.

According to London, Schubert and Washburn (1972) and much later Andrade (2009), one possibility on why people doodle is that “doodling simply helps to stabilize arousal or an optimal level, keeping people awake or reducing the high levels of autonomic arousal often associated with boredom” (Andrade, 2009, p. 4). Scribbling that began during the early childhood phase has become a psychophysiological act during adulthood. Andrade (2009) pointed out that “doodling aids concentration by reducing daydreaming, in situations where daydreaming might be more detrimental to performance than doodling itself” (p. 4). Mason et al. (2007) and Smallwood et al. (2007) in their respective studies found that daydreaming is linked with generally high arousal levels seen during boredom through increased activity in default cortical networks that involve the central executive resources.

What of Scribbling & Its Scribbles

Many young children often scribble on the walls, doors and/or corners at home. Naturally, they will attempt to use the same modality in their classrooms in school. Hence, teachers should take an interest in the scribbles produced by their young charges by allowing them “to express their ideas through scribbling and drawing, as they are fundamental communicative modes of expression (Anning, 2004; Kress, 1997)” (Uddin, 2016, p. 1).

To understand what the scribbles produced by young children mean, Rostron (2021) has postulated that scribbles or “doodles are like fragments of a map that show how someone’s mind works” (para. 13) and constitute “an uninhibited form of self-expression” (para. 15). To interpret what these scribbles are about, Rostron (2021) suggested that one should “look at the basic shapes, the size and spacing of the objects and the style of drawing” (para. 24) as well as the colors used in scribbling. Below are selected scribbles often drawn by children as well as adults and their respective meanings adapted from Rostron’s (2021) interpretation of adults’ scribbles:

Colors: Rostron (2021) explained that “dark colors or heavily shaded areas in a scribble convey a somber mood of serious thought or possibly depression” (para. 43) (see Figure 3); “pale or light-colored scribbles look timid, indecisive or sensitive, while bright colors look more lively and cheerful (para. 44).

Figure 3. Heavily shaded area in a scribble

For Rostron's (2021) interpretation of different colors, readers are advised to read his paper. Here are seven selected commonly used colors in scribbles:

- **Black:** This color "is associated with facts, discipline and what is serious or gloomy" (para. 56).
- **Blue:** This color is associated "with peace, trust, self-discipline, loyalty and spirituality" (para. 52).
- **Brown:** This color is "of down-to-earth practicality and reliability" (para. 55).
- **Green:** This color suggests "natural renewal and change, relaxation, dissatisfaction and growth" (para. 50).
- **Purple (also known as Violet):** This color is "associated with intuition, inspiration and spirituality" (para. 54).
- **Red:** This color "is connected with energy, activity and strong feelings such as anger, love and hate" (para. 46).
- **Yellow:** This color "stimulates the mind, creating excitement and also fear" (para. 49).

Lines: According to Rostron (2021), "straight or curved lines represent masculine or feminine characteristics" (para. 26). In addition, Rostron (2021) also provided further interpretation as follows:

- Straight lines produced by scribblers suggest the tendency "to have strong willpower and self-control and like facts" (para. 25).
- Curvy lines suggest the scribblers "are more flexible, imaginative and emotional" (para. 25).
- Lines drawn in rows show "good organization, a methodical approach and a liking for order and control" (para. 41).
- Lines drawn disorderly (or disorderly scribbles) suggests the scribbler is "a lively person who likes freedom to do things on the spur of the moment but have a tendency to get side-tracked" (para. 41).
- Messy or chaotic lines suggest "problems coping with life or possibly some mental disturbance" (para. 41).

Movement: Where a scribble (of an object or objects) is placed in a scene or appear to be moving towards a direction narrates something about the

scribbler's interests and/or priorities as well as his/her attitude, fear and feelings. The "directional trends indicate attitudes and priorities" (para. 39).

Shapes: Circles, squares and triangles are commonly seen in scribbles and they suggest "needs and motivation" (para. 29). These shapes are hugely symbolic and are believed to be associated with basic needs for love, security and survival (Rostron, 2021). Curves and spirals are associated with continuous circles while right-angled or angular shapes are taken to be parts of squares or triangles.

- **Circles:** Emotional scribblers who prefer harmony and love exhibit their tendency to scribble things with circular or rounded shapes or symbols of love and femininity (e.g., balloons, clocks, cups, eyes, faces, flowers, fluffy clouds, hearts, small animals, trees with rounded canopy, waves, and wheels).
- **Squares:** Scribblers who need security and like to be in control have the tendency to scribble things with square shapes or flat surfaces that symbolize material security (e.g., books, boxes, chairs, doors, fences, ladders, stairs, tables, walls, and windows).
- **Triangles:** Those who need an outlet for their mental and physical energy tend to draw things with triangular or pointed shapes that symbolize masculinity (e.g., arrows, hills, lighthouses, mountains, stars, stick figures, trains and conical Christmas trees).

Object: When a single object is scribbled, the single object represents the scribbler himself/herself (Rostron, 2021). However, when several objects are scribbled, they represent human figures or people who are significant to the scribbler. They may also mean "different aspects of a situation, or parts of the scribbler himself/herself" (para. 34).

Position or Placement: The position/placement of an object (or objects) on a sheet of paper is significant. Rostron (2021) provided his interpretation as follows:

- Top of the paper/page is often associated with dreams, aspirations and ambitions.
- Bottom of the paper/page suggests a need for security or with material concerns.
- Right of the paper/page indicates having to do with future and the outside world.
- Left of the paper/page suggests having to do with the past and related to the scribbler's family.

Size and Space: These "reflect the lifestyle and balance in relationships" (para. 37; for adult scribblers). Rostron (2021) explained further below:

- Size in terms of largeness suggests the scribbler is outgoing, confident, having a busy life, while smallness suggests the scribbler prefers to be an

observing bystander than being a participant (i.e., like to have personal space and prefer a quiet life).

- Space refers to the background scene and it represents the world around the scribbler, who shows it in the scribbling.

Styles and Strokes: The mood and sense of movement in scribbling reflects a scribbler's "temperament, dynamism and self-being at the time, while the strength of the strokes indicates what energy went into the doodling" (para. 40). Rostron (2021) provided further interpretation on this aspect as follows:

- Short, light or sketchy lines suggests the scribbler as sensitive or hesitant.
- Longer, firmer strokes suggest the scribbler is a determined individual who feels strongly about things around him/her.
- "Digging into the paper or going over and over something are indicative that the scribbler is frustrated, obsessed or stuck with a problem" (para. 40).
- "Heavy shading or crisscrossing of strokes suggest depression or worry" (para. 40).

How of Scribbling & Its Scribbles

Although scribbling promotes young children's socio-cognitive growth and provides valuable insights into their thought processes and development, i.e., what they are thinking about what they are scribbling (Baghban, 2007), holding a dialogue with the child scribbler about his/her scribbles can help to enhance his/her socio-cognitive development (Uddin, 2016) in terms of social interaction and cognitive maturity. Dialoguing with young scribblers and asking them questions about what they have scribbled, enable these young children to develop more ideas about their scribbles and they mean. In this way, when these young children are provided opportunities to ponder deeply about what they have produced and share their understandings with others (e.g., parents, teachers, counselors and therapists), they develop a critical mind about their own work.

The processes of dialoguing and scribbling interact with each other, what Uddin (2016) described as "mutually transformative processes", can lead to an ongoing cycle of more complex scribbling and oral narration of the what the scribbles mean to the scribbler concerned. The conceptualization of scribbling as a socio-cognitive activity adds another dimension to the understanding of the important interplay between dialogue and scribbling that provides a deeper understanding of how a young child thinks, feels and acts in a given socio-cultural context.

Conclusion

Understanding the process of scribbling and both the explicit and implicit meanings of scribbles can offer counselors and therapists an alternative therapeutic approach to work with young children with challenging issues of concern. Such children at young age often find it difficult to express their feelings and thoughts verbally. By dialoguing through oral narration of what has been scribbled, a young child is enabled to share his/her thoughts and feelings with an adult (i.e., parent, teacher or counselor), and in turn, has also empowered him/her to act appropriately in whatever the situation the young child is facing.

Called it Dialogic Scribble Therapy, it does not depend on the scribbling process (and the interpretation of the scribbles) alone but also involves some form of dialogue between the counselor/therapist and the child in order to understand the issue of concern to the child scribbler. The therapy offers both the diagnosis based on the scribbles produced by a young child, and with a proper analysis of the scribbles to understand what the child means or is trying to tell us, and the treatment part is to relieve or heal the child's issue of concern based on the results of the interpretation of the scribbles.

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